

Germanium Float-Zone Crystal Growth under Microgravity: Development of In-Space Manufacturing Technologies

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Abstract

Space-based semiconductor crystal growth offers the potential for ultra-high purity materials. However, significant challenges remain. While microgravity substantially weakens gravity-driven convection, Marangoni convection persists, negatively impacting crystal quality through impurity segregation and non-uniform growth.

The Germanium Orbital Optical Semiconductor Experiment (GOOSE), which will fly aboard the Swedish-German sounding rocket REXUS 36, seeks to measure Marangoni convection and its effects on crystal purity, in order to inform strategies for its mitigation. The experiment utilizes a self-designed optical mirror furnace and autonomous controller. It will be the first experiment to measure the critical Marangoni number for Germanium under microgravity conditions.

GOOSE's results serve as a necessary basis for further, more complex experimentation with second- and third-generation semiconductor alloys, which have significant potential to disrupt the semiconductor industry but are very sensitive to convection during production. The paper discusses the setup, methods and preliminary results.

Keywords

Microgravity, Semiconductor, Material Science

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Acronyms/Abbreviations

REXUS	Rocket Experiments for University Students
GOOSE	Germanium Orbital Optical Semiconductor Experiment
EMF	Ellipsoidal Mirror Furnace
FZ	Floating Zone

1. Introduction

Onboard the Swedish-German sounding rocket REXUS 36, Experiment GOOSE flies to approximately 80 km altitude in order to conduct experiments during roughly two minutes of microgravity. During this period, the critical Marangoni number of molten germanium is to be experimentally determined. This material parameter characterizes the transition from stable (subcritical) to unstable (supercritical) thermocapillary flow regimes and has not yet been measured for germanium under microgravity conditions. Its determination is relevant both for space-based and terrestrial crystal growth processes, as Marangoni convection persists independently of gravity and significantly affects melt dynamics [1].

This paper focuses on the development of a compact optical mirror furnace enabling floating-zone crystal growth aboard the REXUS platform. Particular emphasis is placed on the optical, mechanical, and thermal design considerations required to realize a stable, controllable molten zone within the constraints of a sounding rocket environment.

1.1. The Floating-Zone Method

The floating-zone (FZ) method is a crucible-free crystal growth technique particularly suited for high-purity semiconductor processing. In this approach, a cylindrical semiconductor rod is locally melted by a highly concentrated heat source. The molten region is stabilized by surface tension between the adjacent solid sections of the rod, forming a so-called floating zone.

By axially moving the rod relative to the heat source, the molten zone can be moved along the sample axis. Upon resolidification, the material recrystallizes, enabling controlled crystal growth without contact to a container [2] [3]. A schematic illustration of the floating-zone principle is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the float-zone process

1.2. Marangoni Convection

Marangoni convection is driven by surface tension gradients along the free surface of the molten zone. Since surface tension depends on temperature, imposed thermal gradients generate tangential stresses, leading to fluid motion within the melt. Unlike buoyancy-driven convection, this mechanism is independent of gravity. Microgravity therefore provides an environment in which thermocapillary flow can be studied without superimposed gravitational convection.

The Marangoni number is defined as

$$Ma = \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T} \frac{L \Delta T}{\mu \alpha}$$

where $\frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial T}$ denotes the temperature coefficient of surface tension, L the characteristic length (here related to the molten zone length), ΔT the temperature difference across the zone, μ the dynamic viscosity, and α the thermal diffusivity.

The critical Marangoni number marks the transition from steady, axisymmetric (subcritical) flow to oscillatory or unstable (supercritical) convection regimes.

2. Methodology

The experimental determination of the critical Marangoni number relies on controlled variation of the molten zone length. Since the Marangoni number scales with the characteristic length L , different floating-zone lengths are generated during the microgravity phase.

After solidification, the samples are sectioned and analyzed. Flow instabilities manifest as

microstriations within the crystal, which can be correlated to the corresponding zone length during processing. By identifying the transition point between stable and unstable growth conditions, the critical Marangoni number can be inferred.

3. Experiment Setup

The experiment employs a compact ellipsoidal mirror furnace (EMF) designed specifically for operation aboard the REXUS rocket. The furnace uses a halogen lamp positioned in one focal point of a rotational ellipsoid. The emitted radiation is reflected and concentrated into the second focal point, where the germanium sample is located [4] [5] [6]. This principle is schematically shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Functional principle of the EMF internal reflections

Previous microgravity crystal growth experiments conducted by DLR utilized the ELLI furnace system. However, ELLI is no longer operational and, due to size and mass constraints, would not be compatible with the REXUS platform. Consequently, a new compact furnace architecture was developed for GOOSE.

The general EMF setup is composed of the ellipsoid mirror itself, a halogen lamp, the sample holder, a camera observing the float-zone process and additional sensors and valves. This setup is schematically illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic setup of the GOOSE EMF system

3.1. Furnace Design

The furnace is based on a modified EMF design, which employs a novel design approach for significant focus quality improvement. This approach is based on the premise, that usually EMFs produce a virtual focus point in the center of the sample rod. In essence this means, that the interaction point between the light and the sample is slightly out of focus, resulting in a decrease in focus quality. In order to solve this de-focus effect, the ellipsoid axis is offset by the radius of the sample from the rotational axis, around which the 3-D rotational ellipsoid is created. This effectively breaks up the theoretical focus point into a focus ring. This ring then lies exactly in line with the surface of the sample rod, thereby establishing a perfect surface focus around the whole sample circumference. A schematic illustration of this is shown in Figure 4 in order to provide a visual representation of this phenomenon.

Figure 4. Illustration of the focus ring principle - Ellipsoid offset (left) - Resulting focus rings (right)

With this focus ring, ray tracing simulations have been run in order to compare the change in focus quality quantitatively. As demonstrated in Figure 5, the results of these simulations indicate that the relative light intensity at the focus of the adjusted ellipsoid (red) is nearly twice as high as the original (blue).

Figure 5. Raytracing simulation results comparing the novel mirror approach to the unaltered ellipsis

3.2. Experiment Timeline

During the microgravity phase, the furnace is activated and the floating zone is established. The zone length is varied according to a predefined sequence. All relevant parameters are autonomously controlled and recorded. After completion of the microgravity period, the system is powered down and the sample solidifies prior to recovery. This process is shown in Figure 6 as a plot of lamp power over time.

Figure 6. Predefined lamp power curve over the experiment timeframe

4. Verification Results

Preliminary ground-based functional tests demonstrated the successful formation of a stable and controllable floating zone in germanium using the developed mirror furnace. These results confirm the optical focusing capability and thermal performance of the compact EMF design. Float-zones could be achieved for lengths ranging from 2 to 8 mm. An illustration of a stable float-zone is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Camera image of the first stable float-zone

5. Outlook

The successful development of a compact ellipsoidal mirror furnace for sounding rocket applications represents a technological step toward scalable in-space semiconductor processing. The measurement of the critical Marangoni number for germanium under microgravity conditions will provide essential validation data for thermocapillary flow models.

Future experiments may extend this approach to more complex semiconductor systems, including second- and third-generation alloys, where convection control is critical for achieving high crystal quality.

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